

Patient awareness about diabetic retinopathy and visual health

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to analyse the scientific literature on broader patient awareness of diabetic retinopathy (DR).

A scoping review of the scientific literature in PubMed on patient awareness of DR identified 18 manuscripts exploring DR awareness over the past 20 years.

The average patient awareness was 57.6%, indicating that more than half of diabetics are aware of DR and its risks and consequences. Variations were substantial, ranging from 34% to 89%, depending on the type of study, population, educational level, and duration of the disease.

Studies on patient awareness of DR are limited. The degree of awareness is close to 50%, with variation across a relatively wide interval. Educational efforts are needed to improve understanding of the long-term consequences of DR, encourage consultation, and promote early treatment. These efforts should be shared among all stakeholders.

Keywords

diabetes, diabetic retinopathy, patient awareness, scoping review

Introduction

According to the International Diabetes Federation (IDF 2025), diabetes is one of the fastest-growing global health challenges of the recent century. The 2024 estimates for IDF countries indicate 589 million people with diabetes. Alarming is the prognosis for 2050, when the number of people with diabetes is expected to reach 853 million.

Diabetes leads to well-described micro- and macrovascular complications. These complications affect not only a wide range of physiological functions and organs but also the life expectancy and quality of life of patients. One of the microvascular complications that may cause visual impairment and even vision loss is diabetic retinopathy

(DR) (Shukla et al. 2025; WHO 2025). DR is a major factor in severe visual impairment and significantly affects patients' quality of life (Wang et al. 2018).

There are several clinical and scientific reasons to focus attention on diabetic retinopathy. The first is its high prevalence among patients with diabetes (Antonetti et al. 2012). It has been reported that although the incidence of DR declines when diabetes is appropriately treated, micro- and macrovascular complications still progress. Studies indicate that one in three patients with diabetes will develop DR at an advanced age (Wong and Sabanayagam 2020). According to WHO, DR is among the leading causes of vision impairment and blindness worldwide (WHO 2023). The number of adults with DR in 2020 was

estimated at 103.13 million, and by 2045 it is expected to increase to 160.50 million (Teo et al. 2021).

The second reason is the substantial economic burden of DR therapy and its negative impact on patients' quality of life (Zayed et al. 2024). Advanced stages of DR are treated with costly and painful intravitreal injections, often required throughout the patient's lifetime (Benhamza et al. 2024). With disease progression, patients are often non-adherent to therapy, which worsens visual function and may ultimately lead to complete blindness (Javitt et al. 1996).

The third reason is the silent progression of DR, which is quite often unnoticed by patients (Tan and Wong 2023). Preventing DR progression is one of the key strategies to combat the disease (Simó and Hernández 2023). Increasing patients' awareness of DR is important to prevent its onset, delay its progression, and improve the visual health of patients with diabetes (Simó et al. 2020).

Patient awareness is a broad concept encompassing patients' understanding and knowledge of their health status, diseases, and therapy, as well as their essential role in disease prevention and management (Hayashi et al. 1999). It has different dimensions, including awareness of diseases and therapeutic approaches, patients' rights and responsibilities, and psychological and cultural awareness. Factors influencing patient awareness include education, age, insurance coverage, and communication from health-care providers (Örsal et al. 2019).

Exploring patients' awareness of DR as a silently progressing disease is crucial – from the patients' perspective, to prevent the disease and delay visual deterioration; from the payer's perspective, to reduce therapy-related costs; and from the perspective of society as a whole, to ensure a better quality of life for the population with diabetes.

The aim of this study is to analyse the scientific literature on broader patient awareness of diabetic retinopathy.

Materials and methods

A scoping review of the scientific literature on patients' awareness of DR was conducted (Peters et al. 2020). The scoping review approach was chosen because it is relatively faster than a systematic review and provides sufficient information to inform decision-making processes.

Following the recommended steps for a scoping review, the research questions were identified as follows:

- Are patients with diabetes aware of the risks and consequences of DR development?
- What is the level of their awareness?
- What factors contribute to patients' awareness?

The second step, identification of studies, was performed by searching PubMed, one of the most widely used databases for medical literature. The search was conducted using Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) terms during May – July 2024 and included manuscripts published in English over the last 25 years. The keywords used

for the search were “visual health” AND “patient awareness” AND “diabetic retinopathy”.

Studies were included if they met the predefined selection criteria. The selection criteria were organised according to the PICO (Patients, Intervention, Comparator, Outcome) framework. Eligible studies investigated patients with type 1 or type 2 diabetes (Patients), with diagnosed or undiagnosed DR (Intervention), in relation to their awareness of DR risks and consequences (Outcome). A specific comparator was not defined, as both comparative and non-comparative studies were considered relevant for inclusion. Only studies published in English were eligible. All other studies were excluded (n = 57). The study selection process is presented in the PRISMA chart (Fig. 1).

Selected studies were grouped and analysed by author and year of publication; type of study; methods used to assess patients' awareness; type of patients' awareness studied; factors contributing to or influencing awareness across studies; other reported results; and authors' conclusions. A description of the selected 18 articles is provided in Suppl. material 1. These studies include Muecke et al. 2008; Thapa et al. 2012; Çetin et al. 2013; Nathaniel and Adio 2015; Shetgar et al. 2015; Al Zarea 2016; Kizor-Akaraiwe et al. 2016; El Khatib et al. 2017; Haddad et al. 2017; Almalki et al. 2018; Narsaiah et al. 2019; Nwosu 2000; Ma et al. 2020; Venugopal et al. 2020; Lupón et al. 2021; Shrestha et al. 2022; Singh et al. 2022; Pardhan et al. 2024.

Results

The first article was published in 2000 (Nwosu et al. 2000), and the most recent one in 2024 (Pardhan et al. 2024). Notably, authors of eight of the selected manuscripts were from countries with predominantly Asian populations. Table 1 summarises the major characteristics of the selected studies. A cross-sectional design or questionnaire- or interview-based approach was employed in nearly 90% of the studies, while the remaining two were described as an experimental study and a clinical survey. The experimental study compared awareness of visual function decline due to DR among drivers (Ma et al. 2020) and assessed participants' objective self-evaluation. The clinical survey combined a questionnaire with a medical examination (Shetgar et al. 2015). Most studies examined knowledge of the disease and its therapy as the primary domain of awareness. Only three studies addressed cultural aspects in addition to knowledge and focused on psychological awareness.

Table 1. Major characteristics of the selected studies.

Characteristic	Subdivision	N	Relative share (SD)
Type of the study	Cross sectional	8	44%
	Interview/questionnaire	8	44%
	Experimental	1	6%
	Clinical survey	1	6%
Type of awareness	Knowledge	14	77%
	Psychological	1	6%
	Knowledge and cultural	3	17%

Figure 1. Prisma diagram of the study selection process (Page et al. 2021).

Four out of 18 studies did not explore factors that might influence patients' awareness of DR and its related risks and consequences (Table 2). The remaining studies explored more than one factor. Among demographic factors, one study reported that gender does not influence awareness, whereas another found that females tend to be less aware. In all studies, advanced age was considered a positive influence on awareness, likely because DR had already been diagnosed at that stage. Literacy, higher educational attainment (middle or college), and higher income positively influenced awareness. The two studies that explored the influence of disease duration reported opposing results. One study found that the duration of diabetes positively affected awareness, while the other found that early onset had a negative effect. Both findings have plausible explanations. In individuals with long-standing diabetes, DR is more likely to have already been diagnosed, which may contribute to greater awareness through direct experience with the disease and its management. In contrast, in patients diagnosed at a young age, prolonged disease duration may lead to treatment fatigue and reduced awareness. Having a family history of diabetes and DR

increased awareness and promoted good diabetes control, probably due to life experience gained. Only one study explored awareness of DR at the cultural level in a multicultural environment and reported that the Christian religion positively affects awareness.

Table 2. Factors influencing awareness.

Type of the factors	Number of studies	Type of influence	Number of studies
Demographic (age, gender)	6	Positive	5 (advanced age)
		Neutral	2 (gender)
Literacy	3	Positive	Literal
Education	2	Positive	High level of education (college)
Length of the disease	2	Positive	1 long lasting disease
		Negative	1 age at onset
Positive family history of diabetes or DR	2	Positive	2 increase awareness
Religion	1	Positive	Christians' religion
Diabetes control	2	Positive	Good control
Economic welfare	2	Negative	Lower economic class

Legend: 1 – Nathaniel G; 2 – Thapa R; 3 – Muecke JS; 4 – Nwosu S; 5 – Shetgar A; 6 – El Khatib B; 7 – Çetin E; 8 – Singh A; 9 – Almalki N; 10 – Venugopal D; 11 – Pardhan S; 12 – Narsaiah C; 13 – Al Zarea B; 14 – Kizor-Akaraiwe N; 15 – Haddad M

Figure 2. Share of awareness of DR.

Fifteen studies presented quantitatively measured awareness, which varied across wide ranges depending on the type of cohort studied, patient characteristics, and influencing factors. Fig. 2 summarises the findings reported by the authors. It should be noted that when data on unawareness were reported, the corresponding awareness values were calculated by the authors.

The average level of patients' awareness was 57.6%, indicating that more than half of people with diabetes are aware of diabetic retinopathy (DR) and its risks and consequences. Six studies, however, reported awareness levels below 50%. In the study by Shetgar et al. (2015), patients with type 2 diabetes were clinically examined and questioned regarding DR awareness, which was reported at 45.30%. Two studies reported identical awareness levels of 34.9% (Almalki et al. 2018; Venugopal et al. 2020). Both studies were cross-sectional. Almalki et al. (2018) surveyed patients with type 2 diabetes, while Venugopal et al. (2020) did not explicitly state diabetes type; however, cohort characteristics suggest that most participants had a low level of education. The remaining three studies (Kizor-Akaraiwe et al. 2016; Haddad et al. 2017; Narsaiah et al. 2019) were also either cross-sectional or questionnaire based. Their findings indicate that patients demonstrate passive behaviour and tend to rely on physician referral to an ophthalmologist.

Four studies reported a high degree of awareness (Muecke et al. 2008; Çetin et al. 2013; Al Zarea 2016; Singh et al. 2022). Muecke et al. (2008) reported that 86% of respondents were aware that diabetes could damage vision. Although 92% recognised the need for regular ophthalmological visits, only 57% reported attending such examinations, placing this group close to the average awareness level. The studies by Çetin et al. (2013) and Singh et al. (2022) similarly reported high awareness of

DR but a limited understanding of its consequences. According to Singh et al. (2022), 69.5% of participants knew that DR can lead to blindness, and 58.1% were aware that good glycaemic control helps prevent DR. In the study by Al Zarea (2016), 88.99% of questionnaire respondents were aware of visual blurring, and 83.87% were aware of night blindness.

Discussion

In this scoping review, we aimed to explore patients' awareness of DR risks and consequences. We did not identify any other scoping or systematic review addressing this issue using the selected search terms. The absence of comparable reviews may be considered a strength of the present study, but it also confirms the limited research on patient awareness of DR.

Over the 20-year search period, we identified a relatively limited number of 18 eligible manuscripts published in English, eight of which explored Asian populations. This regional predominance may be partly explained by genetic and lifestyle factors, such as increased insulin resistance in Asian populations and the negative impact of unhealthy diets, leading to greater visceral fat at the same body mass index (Rhee 2015). Nevertheless, the available evidence remains limited, indicating that patients' awareness of DR is underexplored. Moreover, several studies have reported that awareness levels are generally low not only for DR but also for other potential eye complications.

With regard to the study questions, the findings indicate that the average level of patients' awareness of DR is 57.6%, suggesting that only about half of patients with diabetes possess adequate knowledge of the condition. When studies assessed only general knowledge of DR,

awareness levels were higher (above 70%); however, when more detailed questions were included, awareness declined to below 50%. Factors influencing awareness included educational level, economic status, religion (in one study only), disease duration and age at onset, and family history. A study conducted in Ethiopia demonstrated that patients with no formal education were approximately 83% less knowledgeable about DR than those with higher education levels, while longer diabetes duration and older age were associated with greater DR knowledge (Dinsa et al. 2025). Furthermore, a cross-sectional study conducted in primary health-care centres in Saudi Arabia showed that patients with higher educational attainment had better knowledge of DR, whereas those with lower income had lower levels of awareness (Alhargan et al. 2019).

Most studies examined knowledge as the core dimension of patients' awareness, which explains why nearly all recommended strengthening educational initiatives to improve understanding of DR risks and consequences. This perspective is strongly supported by the present authors. Educating patients with diabetes should not be regarded solely as the responsibility of physicians. In a low-income region in China, a randomised controlled trial showed that automated SMS reminders containing information about DR, sent 1 week and 3 days before a scheduled eye appointment, increased attendance by nearly 29% and significantly improved patients' DR knowledge, adherence, and satisfaction with care (Chen et al. 2018).

International scientific organisations such as WHO, IDF, and ADA have made significant efforts to develop patient education programmes, whereas national authorities and organisations appear less proactive (IDF 2025; WHO 2025). A study in Fiji demonstrated the long-term value of community-based educational interventions in enhancing DR awareness. A single-day DR awareness training for community health workers significantly increased their confidence in discussing DR and resulted in a sustained increase in patient referrals for DR screening, even 2 years after the intervention (Ram et al. 2022). Another quasi-experimental study showed that implementing a teleretinal screening programme across community health centres increased DR screening compliance by 7.2% (Ha et al. 2025).

A limitation of the present study is the use of a single database – PubMed – with a limited number of search terms. Nevertheless, PubMed is a reliable source of medical scientific literature, and a substantial body of evidence would likely have been identified through this database. The fact that only 75 titles were retrieved further emphasises the limited number of studies focusing on patients' awareness of DR.

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Conclusion

Studies addressing patients' awareness of DR remain limited. Overall, awareness levels are close to 50%, with considerable variation across studies within a relatively wide range. Targeted educational efforts are essential to enhance understanding of the long-term consequences of DR, as well as the need for consultation and early treatment. Such efforts should involve collaboration among all stakeholders – including patients, healthcare providers, policymakers, and community organisations.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

DS – data collection, manuscript selection, review, writing, and final manuscript review; ZM – data collection, manuscript selection, review, writing, and final manuscript review; GP – concept of the paper, methodology, data validation, writing, and final manuscript review.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Description of selected studies

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Data type: pdf

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Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e177932.suppl@1>